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Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of a 16-Membered N₆-Tetradentate Macrocyclic Ligand†

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In this paper the isolation and characterisation of the complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with a 16-membered N₆-tetradentate macrocycle, derived from 2,6-diaminopyridine and dibenzoylmethane, are described.

Experimental

2,6-Diaminopyridine (Koch-Light) and dibenzoylmethane (Aldrich) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Synthesis of complexes: 2,6-Diaminopyridine (0.02 mol) dissolved in a minimum quantity of methanol was mixed with a methanolic solution of anhydrous metal salts (0.01 mol) and then dibenzoylmethane (0.02 mol) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 8 h. After adding concentrated hydrochloric acid (1.0 cm³) it was refluxed for 6 h, and then concentrated to half of its volume and set aside for 3 days. The resulting dark crystals were successively washed with methanol, acetone and ether, and dried under reduced pressure and recrystallised from acetone, (35%). For the copper complexes, a precipitate appeared after 4 h at the reflux temperature.

The nickel and copper complexes were found to be stable upto 200° but the cobalt complexes decomposed above 175°. The complexes were found soluble in DMF, CH₃CN and DMSO.

The nitrate-complexes were prepared from the metal nitrates. Bromo- and thiocyanato-salts were prepared by slowly adding KBr and NH₄NCS solutions to an ethanolic solution of metal chloride with stirring and filtering off KCl and NH₄Cl.

Room temperature magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), infrared spectra in 4 000–650 cm⁻¹ range (KBr) and

650–100 cm⁻¹ range (nujol), electronic spectra (DMF), conductance (Δ_M) in PhNO₂, and molecular weights (in PhNO₂) of soluble complexes by cryoscopic method were determined for elucidation of structure of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the stoichiometry [M(C₄₀H₃₀N₆)X₂] for the complexes, where M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}; and X=Cl, Br, NO₃ or NCS. Lower molar conductance (8–14 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) values suggest non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Molecular weight data of the complexes are consistent with monomeric species.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
	N	X	M	
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	11.81 (11.60)	10.02 (9.80)	8.95 (8.14)	4.92
[Co(L)Br ₂]	10.49 (10.38)	20.04 (19.66)	7.30 (7.25)	5.10
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	10.72 (10.81)	— (15.95)	7.63 (7.59)	4.88
[Co(L)(NCS) ₂]	11.20 (10.92)	—	7.76 (7.67)	4.85
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	11.72 (11.61)	9.90 (9.82)	8.14 (8.02)	3.90
[Ni(L)Br ₂]	10.38 (10.34)	19.76 (19.68)	7.16 (7.14)	3.25
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	10.82 (10.82)	— (15.97)	7.43 (7.47)	3.15
[Ni(L)(NCS) ₂]	10.97 (10.93)	—	7.57 (7.55)	3.28
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	11.64 (11.53)	9.86 (9.74)	8.78 (8.71)	1.82
[Cu(L)Br ₂]	10.21 (10.27)	19.66 (19.55)	7.68 (7.76)	1.76
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	10.63 (10.74)	— (15.86)	8.16 (8.12)	1.75
[Cu(L)(NCS) ₂]	10.70 (10.85)	—	8.16 (8.20)	1.80

*L=C₄₀H₃₀N₆.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of the condensation products of these compounds show various pyridine ring¹, azomethine² and dibenzoylmethane moiety³ vibrations. The bands at ~ 1 590, 1 570, 1 460 and 1 435 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ skeletal frequencies². The other bands appearing at ~ 990, 800, 600 and 410 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ring breathing mode, out-of-plane C–H deformation, out-of-plane and in-plane C–C deformation mode of pyridine ring⁴, respectively. The strong bands at 1 580–1 555 cm⁻¹ are usually associated to ν_{CN} coupled with phenyl ring vibrations⁵. A strong

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band at $\sim 1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder at 1610 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and anti-symmetric $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ vibration^{1,2}, respectively. The absence of absorption bands at $\sim 3300\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows that amino groups of diaminopyridine have been condensed with dibenzoylmethane molecules. The phenyl ring absorptions appear at $1600\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁵. The bands at $900\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to imine- CH_2 absorption of the macrocycle. The ir spectra of the complexes do not show any change in the pyridine ring vibrations, so pyridine nitrogen does not take part in coordination in these complexes¹. Various vibrations of free or coordinated carbonyl groups at $\sim 1700\text{--}1680$ and 670 cm^{-1} are not observed in the spectra of the complexes. Thus, it appears that both the amino groups of 2,6-diaminopyridine react with oxygen atoms of dibenzoylmethane forming a three-carbon atom bridge between the amino groups¹. Thus, in presence of metal salts, a quadridentate macrocycle is formed which coordinates through azomethine nitrogens while pyridine nitrogen atoms do not take part in coordination (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

The changes observed in the spectra of nitrate-complexes show new bands at $\sim 1260, 1015$ and 865 cm^{-1} which are consistent with the monodentate nature of nitrate group⁶. The thiocyanato-complexes show bands at $\sim 2110, 815$ and 480 cm^{-1} assignable to CN, CS and NCS bending, respectively, and are in accordance with the monodentate N-bonded thiocyanato group. The new bands appearing at $\sim 225\text{--}240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ of nitrate group and at $\sim 260\text{--}285\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-NCS}}$ respectively in the far-ir spectra of these complexes⁸.

The far-ir spectra of the chloro-complexes reveal some new bands at ~ 300 (Co-Cl), 285 (Ni-Cl) and 270 cm^{-1} (Cu-Cl), and at ~ 220 (Co-Br) and 215 cm^{-1} (Ni-Br)⁶. The bands at $\sim 430\text{--}495\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes indicate the $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ azomethine vibrations which confirms the coordination of these groups with the metal ions.

Room temperature μ_{eff} values of the cobalt, nickel and copper complexes lie in the range 4.80--

$5.15, 3.15\text{--}3.30$ and $1.75\text{--}1.85$ B.M. respectively which correspond to high-spin distorted octahedral environment around the metal ions^{1,8} arising out of steric interaction between 2,6-diaminopyridine rings and phenyl substituents on the macrocyclic ring.

The electronic spectra (DMF) of the nickel complexes exhibit bands at $\sim 10580\text{--}11000, {}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}(F)$; $11690\text{--}11780, {}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$; and $18180\text{--}18280\text{ cm}^{-1}, {}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{1g}(P)$, with a shoulder on low energy side at $8150\text{--}8530\text{ cm}^{-1}, {}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g(F)$. The shoulder on low energy side can not be spin-forbidden one as it is usually found on the higher side of the first band. This shoulder must have been the result of the split of the first band into two components and indicates tetragonal distortion in these complexes.

The solution spectra of the cobalt complexes are consistent with six-coordinate octahedral geometry⁹ and various bands could be assigned to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ ($8130\text{--}8930$), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ ($15750\text{--}16250$) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ ($18260\text{--}18620\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The assignment of a broad band to ${}^4A_{2g}$ seems plausible since the first band appears at about half of the visible band and thus could not be spin-forbidden⁹.

The copper complexes exhibit two well-discernable bands at $\sim 15550\text{--}17000$ (${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$) and $18280\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ or ${}^3A_{2g}$) which are consistent with distorted octahedral environment around the metal atom^{9,10}. The band separation of the order of 2500 cm^{-1} is in agreement with the proposed geometry. The strong absorptions at $\sim 30800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes may be charge transfer bands due to azomethine group¹⁰.

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Complexes of Oxomolybdenum(v) and Oxovanadium(IV) with Thiocarbohydrazones

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THE complexes of some metal ions with thiocarbohydrazide and its various thiocarbohydrazone derivatives have been reported from this laboratory¹ and by others². In the present paper, we report the preparation and characterisation of some oxomolybdenum(v) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of thiocarbohydrazide (tch) and mono-thiocarbohydrazones derived from acetone (actcH), acetophenone (aptcH), benzaldehyde (bztcH) and furfural (futcH).

Experimental

The ligands and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ were prepared by the reported methods³.

Preparation of complexes. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{LH}=\text{tch}, \text{actcH}, \text{aptcH}, \text{bztcH}, \text{futcH}$; $n=1$ to 4) : $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (0.005 mol) dissolved in methanol (30–40 ml) was treated with 1 : 2 molar ratio of thiocarbohydrazide or thiocarbohydrazones dissolved

either in methanol or methanol–dimethylformamide mixture (30–40 ml). The solution was refluxed for 0.5 h on a steam-bath when products separated out either gradually or on dilution with equal volume of water. The solid complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried (CaCl_2). The purity of the complexes was ascertained by paper chromatography.

$[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{VOL}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous methanolic solution of $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol in 50–60 ml) was treated in 1 : 1 molar ratio with the solutions of aforesaid ligands dissolved in methanol or methanol–dimethylformamide mixture (50–60 ml). The contents were refluxed for 30–40 min on a steam-bath when products separated out either on cooling or on raising pH of the solutions by adding aqueous sodium acetate solution (4–5 ml). The solid complexes were dried as above. The purity of the complexes was checked by paper chromatography.

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$). Electronic absorption spectra (dioxane) were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The analytical and physical data of the compounds are listed in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The complex $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ undergoes substitution reaction with thiocarbohydrazide and thiocarbohydrazones forming μ -oxodioxomolybdenum(v) complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Vanadyl sulphate gave $[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{VOL}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The complexes have poor solubility in benzene and chloroform but dissolve appreciably in dimethyl-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	N	O	H	
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{tch})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	250	26.59 (26.19)	30.12 (30.59)	6.17 (6.55)	3.54 (3.85)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{actc})_4].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	250	21.51 (21.93)	25.30 (25.61)	21.52 (21.96)	4.52 (4.83)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{aptc})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	160	16.52 (16.81)	19.31 (19.64)	37.44 (37.89)	4.23 (4.59)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{bztc})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	175	17.90 (17.68)	20.33 (20.65)	35.80 (35.42)	4.52 (4.08)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{futc})_4].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blood red	250	19.40 (19.02)	22.60 (22.21)	28.12 (28.56)	3.88 (3.19)	Dia.
$[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]^\text{b}$	Black	250	18.51 (18.92)	20.54 (20.81)	4.15 (4.46)	2.50 (2.24)	1.62
$[\text{VO}(\text{actc})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Coffee	250	12.45 (12.94)	28.10 (28.48)	24.22 (24.42)	5.30 (5.63)	1.79
$[\text{VO}(\text{aptc})_2].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Gray	250	9.12 (9.51)	20.53 (20.92)	40.75 (40.36)	5.51 (5.26)	1.79
$[\text{VO}(\text{bztc})_2].\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	210	10.52 (10.80)	23.34 (23.76)	40.50 (40.76)	4.55 (4.27)	1.63
$[\text{VO}(\text{futc})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	250	10.45 (10.85)	23.52 (23.87)	30.45 (30.70)	3.55 (3.86)	1.72

*tch = thiocarbohydrazide, actcH = acetone thiocarbohydrazone, aptcH = acetophenone thiocarbohydrazone, bztcH = benzaldehyde thiocarbohydrazone and futcH = furfural thiocarbohydrazone. ^bAnalysis sulphate, Found : 35.95. Requires : 35.68%.